

Physiological Synchrony in a Collaborative Virtual Reality Task

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Abstract— This paper addresses the need to understand the social dynamics of multiple users collaborating in Virtual Reality (VR) environments. Specifically, we investigate whether the physiological synchrony between leader-follower task roles in Collaborative Virtual Environments is influenced by the user’s previous experience and background. Physiological synchrony is a measure of spontaneous temporal coordination or interdependency between the physiological activity of two or more individuals. Electrodermal activity signals from 8 pairs of users were collected and processed using two different algorithms to measure their synchronization. The results show that physiological synchrony has a moderate correlation with task completion time in VR. Also, the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm is more effective in computing synchrony. The findings show correlations between DTW distance, and task performance measures (completion time, and pre-construct scores).

Keywords— *Physiological Synchrony, Virtual Reality*

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration is a vital process that enables multiple stakeholders to work together towards a common objective. In face-to-face collaboration, participants must be physically present in the same location, which is not always convenient or possible. Therefore, remote collaborative design applications have emerged as a popular alternative in the era of globalization and indeed social distancing. Researchers have explored the characteristics that facilitate successful human collaboration, in the real and virtual worlds. Virtual reality (VR) has provided new collaboration and social interaction opportunities that emulate encounters in the same physical space. One crucial aspect of collaboration, regardless of the setting, is synchrony. It refers to the time dependence of behaviors in human interaction [1].

Synchrony has been studied in various contexts, such as task performance [2], pro-sociality [3], the rapport between therapists and clients [4], [5], team members [6], and mother-child bonding [7] in the real world. When the physiological activity of two or more people “becomes connected or interdependent,” this is known as physiological synchronization (PS) [8]. Studies from psychology have shown that individual physiological responses are externally responsive to - and in some cases even dependent on - the nervous system of others [9], [10]. For instance, previous studies have shown that the most effective collaboration happens when students in the same classroom are in synchrony with each other [11]. Synchrony can be a

significant signal in psychology that sheds light on social dynamics as a possible outcome of collaborative interactions. Numerous areas, such as physical movement [11], facial expressions [12], pupil dilations [13], and neural signals, have shown evidence of synchrony between individuals. Previous studies have also demonstrated that synchronized behaviors between individuals increase cooperation in collaborative problem-solving tasks [6].

However, little is known about synchrony in VR and how it can be used to understand the user in immersive collaborative tasks. Exploring synchrony in VR collaboration may provide new insights into how immersive collaborative systems should be designed and implemented. Inspired by these results, we propose to use measures of physiological synchrony to quantify the experience of leaders and follower synchrony in a Collaborative Virtual Reality (CVR) task.

In this paper, we present the results of a user study involving 22 participants from whom we captured physiological signals gathered via unobtrusive wearable devices. The aim was to quantify the experience of Leader and Follower users in Collaborative VR during task solving. More specifically, we investigate whether the physiological synchrony between the Leader and Follower correlates significantly with -and can thus be used as a proxy for - the mutual response of leader user and follower user on pre-reported background experience (i.e., familiarity, previous technology experience). To assess the viability of our approach, electrodermal activity (EDA) signals from the participants were captured. Hence, we had 11 distinct pairs (dyads). In addition to EDA signals, self-reported measures from the participants were also collected.

We evaluated two algorithms, Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), to measure PS in a collaborative task between a leader and a follower. Using self-reported data, we developed new collaboration metrics, including demographics, technology exposure, and familiarity, to contextualize the PS. Our findings suggest that background details such as demographics, previous technology exposure, use of video conference software, and familiarity influence PS between participants in a VR collaboration. These background factors, when used in combination, impact synchrony between participants.

Fig. 1. Figure showing Synchrony in Collaborative Virtual Environment

II. RELATED WORK

Quality of Experience (QoE) is the “measure of the delight or annoyance of the user’s experiences with an application or service” [14]. Previously, questionnaires were used to evaluate QoE in Collaborative Virtual Reality (CVR). However, researchers are now exploring implicit measures such as physiological signals, facial expressions, head pose, and hand movement directions to gain deeper insights into QoE [15-18]. Since empathy is essential for successful collaboration [19], we propose and utilize Interpersonal Physiological Synchrony (PS) as an evaluation parameter for QoE in CVR. PS measures the physiological association between two individuals [1]. It has been shown to capture the quality of human interactions in one-to-one or one-to-many settings [20]. For example, research has demonstrated that an increase in friends’ EDA signal synchrony leads to greater emotional engagement in social interactions [21].

Researchers have utilized various physiological signals to measure synchrony in collaborative tasks and quantify participants’ experiences in different settings. Accelerometers were used to measure the synchrony response of an audience to a live dance performance [22], while EDA measured through finger wraps was employed to assess engagement levels during video art performances and advertisements [23-24]. EEG has also been used to explore audience engagement during conference presentations [25]. In the context of VR collaboration, researchers have primarily focused on movement synchrony using bodily movements in VR [26-28]. One study even investigated the shared visualization of EEG signals in VR to evoke empathy between collaborators and display a pulsating aura around avatars [29].

Unlike previous studies, the focus is on the leader-follower setting in an immersive collaborative virtual environment. The work investigates the association between the EDA signals of both participants during a collaborative task. Along with HMD (HTC Vive Pro Eye), we use wrist-worn sensing devices (see section III.B) to capture the EDA signals of both participants during the VR task. To the best of our knowledge, no other work has measured the EDA signal synchrony of both users in collaborative VR in this manner. The work most closely related to ours is that presented in [30]. They also measured the EDA of both users collaborating in VR. Their preliminary results show a strong EDA peak with two HMD collaborations resulting in a higher sense of copresence and arousal than in other platforms like two computers (PC-PC) or one HMD-PC. However, they explored only individual EDA peaks and the sample size

consisted of 10 participants. In contrast, our approach considers the EDA data of 16 participants in a Virtual Reality task and measures synchrony between the EDA signals. Moreover, we use pre-filled questionnaires to map the social dynamics in collaborative VR rather than post-experience questionnaires.

III. PARTICIPANTS’ DATA COLLECTION & VR EXPERIENCE

To investigate the experience of leader and follower roles during a Collaborative VR Task, we conducted an experimental study using a collaborative VR application. In this section, details about the participants, the equipment, and the experimental procedure are presented.

A. Participants

22 participants were recruited using a convenience sampling approach. The sample had an average age of (35 ± 11.1) years with a minimum age of 24 years and a maximum of 60 years old. All participants were recruited using a convenience sampling approach from the university (11 females and 11 males).

B. Equipment Used for Collecting Data

Empatica E4 Wristband: The E4 wristband was used to collect the physiological data from participants [31]. The E4 is a multi-sensor device that measures electrodermal activity (EDA), blood-volume pulse (BVP), skin temperature (ST), heart rate variability (HRV), and accelerometer data (ACC). It is small, light, comfortable to wear, and suitable for unobtrusive and continuous monitoring. We charged and synchronized all E4s to a desktop before use. The data was first stored on the E4 and then transferred to a computer for post-processing.

HTV Vive with Handheld Controllers: Two hand-held controllers along with HTC Vive Pro Eye [32] were used for each participant to experience the VR application and facilitate collaboration between two users. During the experiment, the two users were in two different lab rooms at our university. For the collaborative task, they joined the same virtual environment to complete a task, one being the leader and another being the follower as shown in Fig 1. Each user was represented by virtual avatars. Objective performance metrics included: entering time and completion time, eye, head, and hand tracking of participants.

C. Immersive-Multiplayer VR application:

Each participant worked with Windows 10 Pro 64 Bit Edition HP desktops with Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-9700K CPU @ 3.60GHz Processor fitted with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 graphics card. Each desktop is connected to an HTC Vive Pro Eye with hand controllers. Both desktops had the Unity (2019.3.2f.1) VR application and XR Toolkit installed. Task roles were randomly assigned to the participants. Task completion time, with head and hand position data, was also recorded using the application. The Photon Unity Networking (PUN) SDK provided multi-user connectivity in VR through University Network.

TABLE I. MAP SYNCHRONY FROM PRE-CONSENT FORMS

Constructs	Items
Demographics	Original Place
Team Experience	Like Zoom software, and other video conference Software
VR Experience	Previous Exposure to AR, VR
Familiarity	Working together, or known to each other

D. Data Collection Procedure

At the beginning of the session, all participants completed the consent forms. The E4 was fitted to the wrist of the participant's non-dominant hand in accordance with standard practice [33], [34]. It was verified that the E4 was operating correctly, and 5 minutes of resting time was collected to get the baseline readings of all participants before exposing them to the virtual environment or putting on the HMD. The HMD was fitted, and participants were provided an opportunity to familiarize themselves with the applications and controls (as part of a training phase in a bespoke training environment). Then, participants progressed to the shared virtual environment and worked together on the shared task. After completion, both E4 and the HMD were collected from the users.

1) Collected Physiological Data:

As mentioned earlier, the E4 captures EDA, BVP, ST, HRV, and ACC data. In this study, we focused on the analysis of EDA signals to investigate the synchrony between participants during the collaboration task. Even though synchrony among people is reflected in their moving behavior [35], we did not analyze ACC data because both leader and follower were present in different virtual rooms (see Fig. 1) with no similar movement patterns during the experiment.

2) Subjective Data from Pre-filled Forms:

Among several methods for collecting explicit feedback from participants, we used pre-consent forms to get participant consent, as well as some information about the participants, as per Table I. Pre-experience questions were employed to gather explicit feedback regarding participants' background information before the experiment. The construct refers to different aspects of participants' experience during the experiment and items refer to specific questions used to measure the construct.

E. Collaborative VR Experience

The VR experience consisted of two users connected to each other virtually. Each participant was in a different physical room in the faculty building and was accompanied by either the PI or research assistant during the experiment. During the task, the follower works with the leader, following their commands and giving requested blocks to the leader. The leader must describe the color and shape to the follower. To correctly solve the task, they must move 10 shapes (in a specific order) from one room (where the follower is based) to another room (where the leader is based). In the leader's room, the leader completes the puzzle. Each user is restricted to moving around only in their respective virtual rooms. The

follower can pass the objects through the window to the leader as shown in Fig 1. They move around wearing HTC Vive Pro Eye HMD with hand controllers helping them to manipulate the virtual objects with specific keys.

IV. ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

The goal of our work is to quantify the PS of participants in the collaboration VR task using DTW, and PCC algorithms and find whether PS affects overall task performance. To achieve this, we consider the PS between participants' EDA traces. Next, the analysis of EDA data and the obtained results are presented and discussed. We also present the correlations between the synchrony values (obtained through DTW) and task completion time.

A. Pre-processing of EDA Signals

We perform several pre-processing steps to improve the quality of the collected EDA signals from the 11 leaders and 11 followers. After applying a data cleaning procedure, 8 unique EDA pairs remained. The reason for this significant data reduction was that one of the wearable devices used in our study did not record any data for 3 participants. We follow the same pre-processing steps as suggested in [20], [34]: 1) filter the signals for artifact removal, 2) decompose the signal to get further information from the signal and 3) normalize the signals for inter-participant comparison.

1) Normalization:

EDA is a highly individualistic signal [33], which brings challenges in terms of comparison between the users. To enable a fair comparison between the physiological responses of different people, the EDA signals should be normalized [33]. We normalized the EDA traces with equation (1) suggested in [33], where x' is the normalized EDA value, x is the initial EDA value, and $\min()$ and $\max()$ are the minimum and maximum EDA values. The normalized mixed and tonic EDA traces range between 0 and 1 in accordance with standard practice [33].

$$x' = (x - \min(x)) / (\max(x) - \min(x)) \quad (1)$$

B. Synchrony of Physiological Signals

High levels of synchrony have been correlated to higher levels of participants' engagement, group satisfaction, and task performance [2], [10], [35]. Encouraged by this observation, we explore the relationship between the physiological responses of leaders and follower participants and their experiences during the collaboration session of the experiment. To this goal, two different algorithms in the literature were identified for measuring PS between two physiological signals. Then the chosen algorithms were implemented to get the PS between dyads EDA signals. Further exploration of participants' PS was done by extracting and synchronizing general arousal features from participants' individual EDA traces. We then propose four metrics from the pre-experience form to contextualize PS.

1) Approaches for Measuring Synchrony

To quantify the synchrony between the physiological signals, seven measures found in the literature were explored:

Signal Matching (SM), Instantaneous Derivative Matching (IDM), Directional Agreement (DA), Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC), Single Session Index (SSI), Fisher’s z-transform (FZT) [36], [37]; and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW). From there, we chose PCC, and DTW to implement EDA signals to get the resultant distance between two physiological signals. PCC is the fundamental approach that calculates the linear relationship between two continuous signals and displays it as a number between -1 (negatively correlated) and 1 (perfectly correlated). DTW is another algorithm for calculating the degree of similarity between two temporal sequences with different speeds and durations. DTW computes the temporal sequences of each participant’s physiological response signals and gives the total distance. The smaller the distance between two signals, the more the synchrony between them. All these metrics require the signals to be normalized due to individual differences in physiological response levels [34]. Therefore, participants normalized EDA was used (see section 4.A.1) to compute PCC and DTW. Table II shows the normalized EDA signals of a leader and follower participant over time and the synchrony computed with the aforementioned algorithms.

2) Analysis based on Self-reported Prefilled Form

To contextualize the PS between leader and follower, pre-reported experience surveys were derived that reflect the mutual response of participants in terms of self-reported experience. To achieve this goal, questions from the pre-filled consent forms were used. More specifically as per Table I, these included demographics, technical team skills using video conferences, VR experience, and familiarity (known) constructs. To preprocess the survey form, we first obtained a single score for each construct of each response of the two collaborators. The same 4 item constructs for each pair were determined. For instance, if both had the same answers for each construct, then the resultant becomes 1, else 0. We then compute the results as the sum of the four constructs, that is. $(\sum t = \Delta d + \Delta p + \Delta v + \Delta f)$ where: the similarity of participants’ demographics (Δd), perceived team player skills (Δp), VR experience (Δv), and familiarity (Δf) by computing the total score based on their individual output responses.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this section, the results are presented as a function of measuring the correlation between the PS and the total response based on pre-form constructs. Then followed by a discussion on the relationship between PS and each collaborative pair figuratively is presented. Finally, the impact on synchrony and QoE in terms of similarities in skills (VR experience and video conference knowledge) and social factors like demographics and familiarity is discussed.

Table III highlights the various external factors, such as technical skills, demographics, and familiarity impacts physiological synchrony in a virtual simulated environment. As mentioned, this analysis reflects results from EDA signals of 8 valid pairs (16 participants). Pearson correlation (PCC), and DTW algorithms were used to determine PS. Synchrony between individuals can be an important stimulus that provides information about the social dynamics in virtual

Fig. 2. Correlation Plot between DTW distance with Total Pre-construct scores (Negative Correlation) and DTW with Task time (Positive Correlation)

Fig. 3. Pairwise EDA Synchrony data of 8 pairs

interactive collaboration. Since PCC is not robust, we have complemented it with DTW to provide a more accurate measurement of the relationship between two EDA time series signals.

DTW is a robust approach to quantifying PS in our setting therefore the FastDTW [37] algorithm was used to compute DTW. It gives the minimum warping path between two EDA signals of the dyads as depicted in Table III. DTW distance is a measure of dissimilarity between two-time series, so a greater DTW distance indicates less similarity or synchrony between the two series. Therefore, if the physiological synchrony between two individuals or groups is high, the DTW distance should be low, and vice versa. The total score from the individual pre-filled form constructs is computed by applying an AND logic gate to the individual responses.

Table II shows used pre-filled questions to gather explicit feedback regarding participants’ background information. The construct refers to the mutual response of the dyads and their PCC and DTW values of (EDA signals) with genders. The time taken by each pair to complete the collaborative task in the virtual environment is also provided. Results show that when the total score of pre-filled metrics (t) reaches 3 or more,

the DTW distance between participants' EDA values decreases, indicating higher synchrony (Table II). A strong negative correlation ($r=-0.73$) between DTW distance and pre-construct scores (Fig 2) was discovered, meaning that higher pre-construct scores correspond to less DTW distance, and vice versa. Interestingly, participants with higher synchrony completed the task quicker than others with less synchrony. A moderate positive correlation ($r=0.33$) between DTW distance and task completion time (Fig 2) was observed, indicating that PS determined through DTW is positively correlated with task completion time. We see that PS enhances collaboration and leads to more efficient and quicker task completion. When individuals experience physiological synchrony, it indicates a higher level of coordination, shared understanding, and mutual engagement and therefore they complete the task faster than other pairs improving the task performance.

Furthermore, Fig 3 shows the EDA signals of the eight pairs of participants and how each varied during the collaborative VR task. It is interesting to note that two pairs Pair2 and Pair 6 were negatively correlated based on PCC value whereas the other six pairs had some correlation with each other. Even though figuratively, Pair 1 (PCC = 0.7) and Pair 8 (PCC =0.22) as positive PCC, the DTW distance is more than other pairs. Since EDA signals are temporal signals, DTW seems to be an effective algorithm to evaluate PS rather than PCC.

Instead of using the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC), we utilize the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance method to quantify Physiological Synchrony. The findings suggest that when we compare the temporal patterns of physiological signals between individuals using DTW and PCC, DTW is a more flexible and versatile method. However, due to the small sample size, we plan to validate these results with more participants in the future.

While the main findings are based on a small sample size, the obtained results suggest a hypothesis for future exploration. While prior research on synchrony has largely been conducted in in-person environments, our study uniquely utilized remote virtual reality (VR) technology to investigate this phenomenon. We offer evidence that physiological synchrony (determined through DTW) in VR improves task experience and is important in determining the quality of distributed collaboration. In addition, our study has demonstrated that the greater the degree of shared background factors between collaborators, the greater the level of synchrony between them. Furthermore, we have identified various methods for measuring EDA (electrodermal activity) synchrony in collaborative group settings.

A. Discussion

The use of PS to quantify participants' engagement and bonding during the collaboration session of the experiment opens new opportunities. Pre-experience background information allowed us to evaluate the effectiveness of synchrony in improving their collaborations. We believe that our approach can be extended to systems designed for

TABLE II. CONSTRUCTS WITH SYNCHRONY FROM EDA

Constructs to Map Synchrony form pre-and post-Questionnaire									
N	Pre-Form Constructs					PS of EDA		Pair	Time
	Δd	Δp	Δv	Δf	Σt	PCC	DTW	G-G	Task
1	0	1	0	0	1	0.70	2309.7	F-M	19:39
2	0	1	0	0	1	-0.64	252.2	M-M	33:22
3	1	1	1	0	3	0.56	49.5	F-F	8:12
4	1	1	1	0	3	0.86	145.0	M-F	10:28
5	0	1	0	1	2	0.30	554.6	F-M	08:10
6	0	1	0	0	1	-0.48	1125.7	F-F	22:11
7	1	1	0	1	3	0.22	120.2	F-F	12:19
8	0	1	0	0	1	0.27	1751.8	M-M	11:46

different task-roles cardinality settings (e.g., many-to-many) and different location settings (e.g., collocated, distributed audience), and different task roles as suggested in [27].

This research demonstrates that the impact of common factors, such as ethnicity, VR technology exposure, familiarity (closeness), and team-building skills, on the experience of VR collaborative tasks is significant. We found that the more these factors were mutual between collaboration pairs, the greater their influence on task performance, with pairs who shared similar backgrounds achieving better task completion times compared to those with diverse backgrounds.

Overall, the findings enhance our understanding of background factors that influence people when collaborating with a remote partner via different communication media. This study suggests that collective intelligence will depend on the mutual technical experience, familiarity, and proficiency of the participating individuals. This shared technical experience enables smoother communication and seamless collaboration. Extrapolating from our results, one can argue that mutual factors of team members contribute to enhancing the quality of collaboration and may promote better communication and social interaction during collaborative problem-solving. Therefore, this study suggests that as distributed collaboration becomes more common, the mutual technical experience of the participants will play a significant role in collective intelligence for solving collaborative tasks.

VI. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE WORK

Although this work offers promising prospects for collaborative VR tasks for dyads, we acknowledge some limitations that leave room for future research to refine and extend our findings. In our future work, we plan to test additional users and secure more data to further verify these findings and identify artifacts of collaboration based on physiological signals. Although this reduction is high, it is still comparable to other similar studies [27], [30]. In this work, we demonstrate that in the shared VR environment, the physiological synchrony is influenced by participants' external background factors.

Our study has limitations that offer opportunities for future research. For example, our findings were observed in newly formed dyads in the laboratory with a small sample size. It remains to be seen whether our findings will generalize to teams that are ongoing or in which there is greater familiarity among members, as in the case of

distributed teams in organizations. We encourage future research to test these findings in the field within organizational teams.

We would also like to extend the VR application implemented for this study and collect more contextual data with a larger sample size to validate these results. This information in combination with the synchrony of other physiological responses (like HRV, IBI, and Pupil Dilations) would reveal a better understanding of physiological synchrony in the shared context.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we report our findings in exploring the experience of leaders and followers during VR collaboration using wearable physiological sensors. We performed our analysis on data collected from 8 leaders and 8 follower members, coupled into 16 participants after the pre-processing of the data. Our results show that physiological synchrony between leader and follower is associated with participants' external background as shown by their EDA level. Moreover, we found DTW provides better results than PCC based on task completion time and total pre-construct scores. This finding opens opportunities to explore the implications of synchrony in this context. We advance previous research by providing evidence that EDA synchrony is interpretable in virtual-world collaboration settings by connecting changes in synchrony to changes in participants' external factors. Our findings outline the novel opportunities for the design and implementation of leader-follower collaborative feedback systems and used synchrony as a parameter for evaluating collaboration in VR.

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